

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Pharmacological and pharmacognostical aspect of *Prosopis juliflora*: A review

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Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2020.8.1.0219>**Abstract**

Prosopis juliflora also called as mesquite or Velayati babul, found all over the world specially in semiarid and arid areas. It is a competitive weed and has been declared as noxious in several countries. WHO found that herbal medicines are used traditionally for the treatment of diseases, nearly 80% of the population utilize plants due to their less side effects and easy availability as compared to allopathic systems of medicine. *Prosopis juliflora* belongs to family Leguminosae and also has an effective role as traditional medicine. Every part of this species contains a large number of phytoconstituents mainly flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, phenolics, terpenes and saponins. The plant possesses some pharmacological activity like antibacterial, anti-pustule, antitumor, larvicidal, anthelmintic, antimicrobial, anti-rheumatic, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antioxidant, antimalarial activities. Despite of its various uses, it is a serious invasive weed and is cytotoxic in nature. Due to ingestion of *Prosopis juliflora* pods, a neurological disorder “Cara-torta” is most common in the ruminant animals like goats which directly affect mitochondria of nerve cell. So, this article is an aggregate of all the details and information of *Prosopis juliflora* plant published in different books and journals.

Keywords: Alkaloids; Cytotoxic; Invasive; Mesquite; Pharmacological activities; *Prosopis juliflora*

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1. Introduction

Prosopis juliflora is one of the most invasive species of India and the world, which belongs to the family Leguminosae and subfamily Mimosoideae and has 44 species across the world [1,2]. Traditionally, *P. juliflora* is utilized for curing diarrhea, cold, dysentery, flu, inflammation, measles, hoarseness, sore throat and for the curing and healing of wounds [3]. Woods of *P. juliflora* species used as a source of charcoal and activated carbon and also in the manufacturing of paperboard and fiber for paper and hardboard industries. *P. juliflora* is also used as pods for animal feed and the flowers are used by bees for honey production [4,5,6]. It is a competitive weed and also called as a noxious weed in several countries because the tree dries out the soil and compete with every plant, especially grasses in the dry areas [1,7]. Drought tolerant genes have been identified in *P. juliflora* using expressed sequence tags and these genes are used as drought tolerance genes in various transgenic crops or plants [8]. Medicinal uses of *P. juliflora* have been demonstrated in many studies and the extracts of different parts of *P. juliflora* possess numerous pharmacological activities such as antimicrobial, antioxidant, antimalarial, larvicidal, insecticidal, antitumor, anthelmintic, antiemetic and cholinesterase inhibiting activity [9]. From ethnopharmacological studies, it was found that *P. juliflora* is used as an astringent, in rheumatism and as remedies against scorpion stings and snakes bite [10]. The plant is also a rich source of phytoconstituents, especially alkaloids, saponins and flavonoids. The pharmacological and biological activities signify the importance of this plant as a possible candidate for deriving phytomedicines [11].

2. Botanical information

Table 1 Taxonomical classification.

Kingdom	Plantae
Phylum	Angiosperms
Class	Dicot
Order	Fabales
Family	Leguminosae
Subfamily	Mimosoideae
Genus	<i>Prosopis</i>
Species	<i>Juliflora</i>

2.1. Synonym

Mimosa juliflora, *Prosopis pallida*, *Prosopis inermis*, *Prosopis horrida* [1].

2.2. Common Name

Honey Mesquite and Mesquite [12].

2.3. Geographical source

P. juliflora is a preserving and bionomic tree species found in semi-arid and arid places in the world. In India, it occurs throughout the area from Punjab to Tamil Nadu and from Gujrat to the dried region of Orissa. On earth, different species of *Prosopis* are found with differences in their physical, chemical and physiological properties. The states in India where this species mainly occur are: Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Haryana, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and Orissa.

2.4. Vernacular Names

Hindi - Velayati babul, Velayati Babool, Velayati khejra; Gujrati - Gando baval; Marathi - Velayati kikar; Marwari - angrezi bavalija; Kannada - Bellari jali; Tamil - Velikaruvel, Velimullu [13].

2.5. Morphology

P. juliflora is either in the form of tree or shrub of various sizes. It is mostly xerophilous, spiny, armed and aculeate. The glands are present at the joint of leaflets and pinne. The legume is straw-yellow or brown in colour (8-29 cm long, 9-17 mm wide, 4-8 mm thick) after drying and straight with apex which is curved inward and sometimes falcate, compressed, linear, stipulate, rectangular to subquadrate. Plant has spines that are 0.5-5 cm long, not on every part, solitary or paired [14,15].

2.5.1. Tree form and size

Tree size and form vary from species to species and also depend on genetic and environmental influences. *P. juliflora* normally reaches a maximum height of 12 m, but can also reach up to 20 m under favorable condition.

2.5.2. Seeds

They are epigeous in germination. The cotyledons are fleshy and are first seed leaves that also exist after the first true leaves have formed, they are green or pale green in colour [15].

2.5.3. Wood

The woods of *P. juliflora* are diffusely porous in its gross structure and are (bark) pale brown in colour when present in dried form. At microscopic level *P. juliflora* contain fibers (48%), vessels (18%), rays (18%) and axial parenchyma (16%) [13].

2.5.4. Leaves

They are bipinnate in nature and have nodes, petiole and rachis (5-20 cm) long. The leaves are medium to large, 10-20 cm long. Leaflets are 8-18 mm long, either elliptic-oblong, linear- oblong or ovate in shape, with pointed apex. Glands are sessile with an apical pore, cuculiform and they are present at the junction of pinnae or the junction of leaflets [14].

2.5.5. Flowers

Flowers are long, spike like inflorescence known as racemes and are cylindrical in shape. They are yellow to yellow-white in colour. Inflorescences (9.5-16.5 cm) equal in length to the leaves, or slightly longer or slightly shorter with 237-344 number of flowers. Flowers are sterile, actinomorphic, pentamerous and hermaphrodite in nature. Inflorescence contains various parts like calyx, corolla, pistils, petals, stamen and pedicel [15].

2.5.6. Fruit

This species also belongs to the Leguminosae family because of the arrangement of different parts of fruit. The fruit is an indehiscent legume and has incurved apex, with or without parallel margins. The edges of the fruit have no parallel margins with 16-28 cm length, 14-18 mm width and 6-10 mm thickness. The pods which we called fruit are green in colour when immature and yellow when they are fully mature in nature. They are flattened to subquadrate in section and acuminate and stipitate, compressed to sub-compressed and sub- moniliform.

2.5.7. Thorns

Axillary spines are present which are divergent and geminate. They are straight, uni or multimodal, solitary and paired on different or solitary and paired on the same branch. Trees vary in the size and number of thorns, which either are absent or present or not on all branches [16].

2.6. Physiochemical properties

Different parameters such as ash value, moisture content of *P. juliflora* are $6.1 \pm 1.36\%$ in green pods, $7.3 \pm 1.88\%$ in dry pods, 4.8 ± 1.02 in leaves, 8.9 ± 1.19 in bark and 61.3 ± 5.44 in green pods, 26.3 ± 4.09 in dry pods, 56.0 ± 6.38 in leaves, 35.0 ± 4.99 in bark respectively [17].

3. Traditional use

Prosopis genus is used in the old days, for various activities and has a lot of biological, agricultural, chemical and medicinal uses. People use it for medicinal purposes in rheumatism, as remedies against snake bite and scorpion stings. Also, powdered flowers mixed with sugar are used by pregnant women for safety purposes in various regions. *P. juliflora* is also active against *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* which was isolated from symptomatic patients so used to treat gonorrhoea.

Other *Prosopis* species are also used as diuretic and treat ocular and hepatic problems [18]. *Prosopis Africana* (leaves, bark twigs, roots) is used to treat dermatitis, bronchitis, tooth decay, malaria, stomach cramps and dysentery. In some areas, it is also used to treat sore throat, tooth decay and heal wounds and cuts [19]. *Prosopis farcta* in Iran is used traditionally for treating cardiac pain and angina pectoris [20]. *Prosopis cineraria* is used for curing earache, leprosy, dyspepsia, leukoderma, asthma, dysentery etc. [21].

4. Phytochemistry

The air-dried leaves of *P. juliflora*, also known as Velayati Kikar were evaluated for phytoconstituents that are alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, saponins and tannins [22]. Anti-bacterial, anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antiviral are some pharmacological activities shown only by alkaloids and saponin. *P. juliflora* or we can say it as mesquite, its different parts such as pods, flowers, leaves, stem and seeds contain a large class of metabolites. Pods and leaves contain a large amount of phytoconstituents as compared to other different parts of *P. juliflora* [3].

In the year 2012 Singh perform the phytochemical analysis on leaves, pod, flower, root and stem of *P. juliflora* and found the presence of various phytochemicals in varying concentrations in different parts. Phytochemical analysis revealed that the pods and leaf show the presence of alkaloids, steroids, terpenoids, flavonoids, tannins and phenolics. The flower extract shows the presence of alkaloids, steroids, terpenoids, flavonoids and phenolics. Also stem shows minimum concentration of compounds like phenolics, terpenes, flavonoids and steroids, while roots extracts show the presence of phenolics, tannins, flavonoids, steroids, alkaloids, terpenes and saponin. Phlobatannin and cardiac glycoside are absent in all parts of the plant, whereas saponin is only found in roots [23].

Extraction is the initial step of various phytochemical screening or for the isolation of phytoconstituents. Different solvents are used in increasing order of polarity for better extraction of all secondary metabolites i.e. petroleum ether, benzene, chloroform, ethyl-acetate, ethanol and water. Here, petroleum ether is least polar and water is most polar solvent [24].

Table 2 Chemical structure of various constituents in *Prosopis juliflora* with pharmacological activity

S. no.	Classification/ Compound	Compound	Biological activity	Ref.
1.	Alkaloid (Julifloridine)		Not specified	[25-26]
2.	N-methyl julifloridine		Not specified	[25-26]
3.	Juliprosopine		Anti-leishmanial Activity, Anti- dermatophytic activity, Antibacterial activity	[27-32]
4.	Juliprosine		Antibacterial agent, Antimalarial activity, Antifungal activity, DNA- binding activity	[31-33]

5.	Isojuliprosine		Antifungal activity	[27]
6.	Secojuliprosopinal		Plant growth inhibitor	[34]
7.	Juliprosinene		Antibacterial agent	[27]
8.	Flavanoid ((-)-Mesquitol)		Antioxidant	[35]
9.	Amino acid (L-tryptophan)		Plant growth inhibitor	[36]
10.	Glycoside (Syringin)		Plant growth inhibitor	[37]

11.	Enterolignan Precursor((-)- lariciresinol)		Plant inhibitor	growth [37]
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The metabolites like shikimic acid metabolites ((-)-lariciresinol, phenylpropanoids) and piperidine alkaloids (secojuliprosopinal) from *P. juliflora* with allelopathic properties result from two major biosynthetic pathways i.e. shikimic acid pathway and acetic acid or polyketide metabolic pathway through the lysine amino acid pathway [38]. Leaves of *P. juliflora* contain a high number of alkaloids such as juliflorine, julifloricine, julifloridine, juliprosinene, juliprosine, juliprosopine and mesquitol²⁴ and phenolic derivatives [39]. Some chemicals like syringin, (-)-lariciresinol, L-tryptophan, juliprosopine, juliprosine, and juliprosopinal are water soluble and released into its space through the leaves by rain water [40]. The chemical composition of all phytoconstituents and their concentration are not same in all parts but difference is noticed from parts to parts or organ to organ within the developmental cycle [41]. Bark of *P. juliflora* contains quercetin, 4,7-dimethylether, kaempferol 4-O-methylether, retusin, L-mannopyranoside which exhibit antifungal activity. It also contains 3-oxo-juliprosopine, secojuliprosopinal which shows anti-inflammatory activity. Different parts other than leaves and bark like pods, heartwood, flower, roots also contain some constituents which also have some biological activity [9].

Table 3 Plant metabolites (in gram) extracted by using various solvents from dry plant material [23].

Solvent →	Hexane	Chloroform	Acetone	Ethanol	Water	Total
Plant part ↓						
Leaf	1.31	2.85	0.96	5.63	4.97	15.72
Stem	0.82	1.51	0.68	3.08	2.48	7.92
Pod	1.05	2.23	0.72	5.55	5.84	15.30
Flower	0.95	2.62	0.77	5.04	4.30	13.68
Root	0.74	1.79	0.56	4.04	3.35	10.48

4.1. Wood

The woody biomass contains several constituents and can be classified into cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and extractives with levels 40-45%, 25-30%, 11-28% and 3-15% respectively [42].

4.2. Fruit

The pulp contains 56% of the total weight of the fruit. Sucrose (45%) is the very soluble constituent of pulp representing 90% of all soluble sugar present. Other reducing sugars also present that are glucose, fructose, inositol, raffinose and xylose etc [43,44].

4.3. Leaves

In leaves essential amino acid (AA) are maximum but low S-containing AA are present. Alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, polyphenols and chemical constituents are also present. The constituents of the leaves can be classified into nitrogen free extract, basic extractives and mineral elements. Basic extractives present in the leaves are protein (26.3%), fiber (24.8%), extract (8.5%), ash (1.4%) and mineral elements such as micronutrients and macronutrients [45,46].

Table 4 Phytochemicals present in the extracts obtained from various parts of *P. juliflora* [23].

Plant parts → Phytochemicals ↓	Leaf	Pod	Flower	Stem	Root
Tannin	+	+	-	-	++
Phenolics	+++	+++	+++	+	++
Flavonoids	+++	++	+++	+	++
Cardiac glycosides	-	-	-	-	-
Alkaloids	++	+++	++	-	+
Terpenes	++	++	+	+	++
Steroids	+++	++	+	+	+
Saponin	-	-	-	-	+

“+” low concentration, “++” moderate concentration, “+++” high concentration, “-” absent

5. Pharmacological activity

P. juliflora showed antibacterial activity against strains of *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Shigella sonnei* and other phytopathogenic agents [27]. Furthermore, investigated that Juliflorine possesses immuno- modulating activity when assayed in rabbits using Freund’s complete adjuvant (FCA) containing Listeria hemolysin (antigen), administered intramuscularly in various concentration and dose dependent immune response was observed [47]. Choudhary *et al.*, demonstrated the acetylcholinesterase inhibitory potential in juliflorine alkaloid isolated from *P. juliflora* [48]. Also, pollen of juliflora species is an important source of flavonoids, which are considered as natural antioxidants [49]. The *in-vitro* antiplasmodial activity was studied in ethanolic extract of numerous south Indian medicinal plants against *Plasmodium falciparum* and found that flower, leaf and bark extracts of *P. juliflora* showed IC₅₀ values of more than 100 µg/ml [50]. Due to its better antioxidant activity, it is also useful in controlling inflammatory diseases, cancer and diabetes [51].

Figure 1 Pharmacological Activities of *P. juliflora*

5.1. Antibacterial activity

P. juliflora contains a large number of alkaloids in various parts that were tested for their antibacterial activity using disc diffusion technique on some gram-positive and gram-negative bacterial strains. The extract of leaves of *P. juliflora* showed better activity as compared to other plant parts. Klebsiella was found to be more susceptible bacteria than Acinetobacter and Alcaligin [33]. Also, a dose-dependent inhibitory activity was observed in concentration range of 50 mg/ml to 300 mg/ml and results demonstrated that the extract showed good inhibitory activity against all the bacterial strains like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *M. luteus*, *S. aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Salmonella typhimurium* [52]. Similarly, well-diffusion test was carried out for *P. juliflora* methanolic extract on Gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus* sp. and *Streptococcus* sp.) and Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli* and *Klebsiella* sp.) by Raghavendra *et al.* to study the inhibitory action of the extract on various bacteria. Widest zone of inhibition was shown by green leaves (22 and 19 mm zone of inhibition) as compared to dry leaves (22 and 19 mm zone of inhibition). The study findings concluded that gram-positive bacteria are more affected than gram-negative bacteria. Also, methanol extract of green leaves of *P. juliflora* was more effective as compared to dry leaves [24].

5.2. Antimalarial activity

Due to the development of resistance to some antimalarial drugs that are used to treat malaria and fever, numerous plants have been examined for *in-vitro* antiplasmodial activity which are used traditionally to treat malaria. According to a study by Simonsen *et al.*, *P. juliflora* ethanolic extracts from flower and fruit showed an IC₅₀ value of 24 µg/ml and possess good antiplasmodial activity [53]. In another study, *in-vivo* antimalarial potential has also been evaluated in the formate salts of julifloridine and juliprosopine isolated from *P. juliflora* and compared with chloroquine. Juliprosopine was found to be more potent at 2 mg/kg as compared to chloroquine at 50 mg/kg [54].

5.3. Anti-tumor activity

Approximately 60 anticancer drugs were derived from different plants; mainly contain vinblastine, vincristine and vinorelbine which are sold in the market. Mani *et al.* studied *in vitro* anti-tumor potential in alkaloids present in leaves extract of *P. juliflora*. The extracts were assayed in different concentration (10 to 100 µg/ml) using MTT based cytotoxicity assay, which was done after 24, 48 and 72 hours exposure of T-cell leukemia (Molt-4) (1×10⁶ cells/ml medium) and also assayed on mitogen-stimulated T-lymphocyte cultures derived from the venous blood of healthy volunteers. It was found that extract exhibits high toxicity towards the cancerous cells as compared to normal cells i.e. 72.65 % and 46.51 % cytotoxicity for cancerous and normal cells respectively. The study findings further demonstrated that cytotoxicity against T-cell leukemia depends on time and dose with a lack of genotoxicity [55].

5.4. Larvicidal activity

Yadav *et al.* evaluated extracts of different plants to facilitate the development of highly effective extract for mosquito control. Leaves of *P. juliflora*, *Malvastrum coromandelianum*, *Vernonia cinerea* and *Hyptis suaveolens* were collected and evaluated for larvicidal activity in different solvents like methanol, isopropanol, dimethyl sulfoxide, acetone and water. *Vernonia cinerea* in acetone showed maximum activity followed by *P. juliflora* in methanolic solution [56]. Also, in another study, acetone extract of *Vernonia cinerea* and isopropanol extract of *Callistemon viminalis* were found to be most effective against *Aedes albopictus* larva with LC₅₀ value of 64.5 ppm 71.34 ppm respectively. *P. juliflora* acetone extract was also found to be effective oviposition-deterrent for the control of *Aedes albopictus* mosquito at 100 ppm [57].

5.5. Anthelmintic activity

A lot of animals in tropical regions are died due to nematode infection and synthetic anthelmintics are not capable of curing the infection. *P. juliflora* is a plant which is easily available in harsh environmental conditions and is fast growing and drought resistant. In the year 2011, Rechab *et al.* demonstrated anthelmintic activity in the ethanolic extract of both leaf and root of *P. juliflora* and further compared with standard drug Albendazole. Results showed that the ethanolic extract of leaves is more effective in anthelmintic activity than the roots extract whereas equally effective when compared with synthetic drug Albendazole. The presence of saponins, condensed tannins and alkaloids in the extract are the main causes of anthelmintic activity. Thus, these phytoconstituents can be a favorable source for veterinary drug development to cure nematode infection [58].

5.6. Antifungal activity

Antifungal potential in *P. juliflora* was investigated by Raghavendra *et al.* using poisoned food technique against fungus *Alternaria alternata* (cause brown spot of tobacco) in different solvents (petroleum ether, chloroform, benzene, ethanol,

methanol and aqueous). Methanol and ethanol extracts showed maximum antifungal property among all other solvent extracts. For isolation of alkaloids, methanol extract was further fractionated and compared with synthetic fungicides (blitox, captan, dithane M-45 and thiram) for antifungal activity at a minimum inhibitory concentration of 1000 ppm. The alkaloid extract at 1000 ppm showed better fungicidal activity and was effective at a low dose as compared to synthetic fungicides [59]. Dale, in his work studied that *P. juliflora* contain a majority of alkaloids with various biological activities that was active against a wide range of seed-borne fungi. Alkaloid extract of *P. juliflora* was amended with all the chemical fungicides at 1.5 g/L and 1 g/L. The combination of chemical fungicides amended with alkaloid extract showed highly significant antifungal activity compared to chemical fungicides tested alone at the particular dosage. Finally, the result recommended that the extract reduce the dose of chemical fungicides and increase the inhibition of seed mycoflora efficiently [60].

5.7. Antimicrobial activity

P. juliflora crude extracts, alkaloid-enriched fraction and isolated alkaloid was explained by dos santos *et al.* that was evaluated for antimicrobial potential by in-vitro methods. In 1999, Satish *et al.* described the potential use to combat microorganisms in crop plants and Caceres *et al.*, studied the treatment of gonorrhoea by using tincture of *P. juliflora*. For that plant material was macerated in 50% alcohol and the tincture tested for in-vitro activity by measuring the inhibition zone. The leaf extract or tincture showed 9.6 mm of inhibition which was maximum and most active against *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* (Isolated from symptomatic patient) [61]. Besides the studies on microorganisms that affect humans, Satish *et al.* found that antibacterial property was only found in the aqueous extracts of *P. juliflora*, *Lawsonia inermis* and *Oxalis corniculata*. *P. juliflora* leaves have antibacterial activity against various *Xanthomonas* sp. (inhibition zone of 18-23 mm) comparable to bacterimycin and streptomycin and manage diseases in several crops [62]. In 2013, dos santos *et al.* described in-vitro antimicrobial activity to evaluate pods of *P. juliflora* as feed additives for ruminants which contain alkaloid enriched fraction for study. Chloroform extract of *P. juliflora* pods contains alkaloids which have in-vitro antimicrobial activity against *Micrococcus luteus* (MIC = 25 µg/ml), *Staphylococcus aureus* (MIC = 50 µg/ml) and *Streptococcus mutans* (MIC = 50 µg/ml) and gas production have been evaluated with monensin as the positive control. The results showed that extract produces less gas during fermentation in ruminants as compared to monensin [32].

5.8. Antioxidant activity

It is observed that flavonoids and phenolic compounds are significantly important for describing antioxidant properties of various plant pollens. The compounds with phenolic hydroxy group have antioxidant property specially, the compounds with dihydroxy at 30th and 40th position of the B ring of flavonoid compounds [63]. *P. juliflora* honeybee collected pollen has higher antioxidant properties than *Amaranthus hybridus* pollen [64]. Antioxidant activity was seen by Prasad *et al.* in aqueous leaf extract of *P. juliflora* using rat liver enzymes. It was found that when the rats are fed-up with 5% aqueous extract, it showed protective activity against hepatotoxicity induced by *S. aureus* [65]. Furthermore, Sirmah *et al.* did an experiment to check whether *P. juliflora* extract (heartwood) could be used as a source of antioxidant compounds for food, cosmetics or for pharmaceutical application. Results concluded that presence of flavonoids (4-O-methyl-gallocatechin) and (-)-mesquitol as the main secondary metabolite in *P. juliflora* extract are a good source of antioxidant compound [35].

5.9. Antipyretic activity

Ethanol extract of *P. juliflora* reveals the presence of major phytoconstituents like flavonoids, alkaloids, anthraquinones, quinines, tannins, Leucoanthocyanidin, and Ellagic acid glycosides, were tested for brewer's yeast induced hyperthermia in rats. The extract has been explored as potential and effective antipyretic activity at different tested dose level. Gopinath *et al.* utilized the extract of *P. juliflora* in two concentrations i.e. 250 and 300 mg/kg p.o. to study antipyretic action of *P. juliflora* and compared them with standard paracetamol (150 mg/kg p.o. in WFI). Rectal temperature was noted at 2,3,4 hours intervals and significant decrease in rectal temperature was observed indicating antipyretic potential of *P. juliflora* [66].

5.10. Antiemetic activity

Ul Hasan *et al.* studied methanolic extract of leaves of *P. juliflora* and extract of some other plants (*Adenanthera pavonina*, *Peltophorum roxburghii*, *Prosopis cineraria*) for antiemetic activity and compared with chlorpromazine. Copper sulphate (50 mg/kg, p.o) was used as an emesis inducer in male chicks of four days age. The result was concluded by calculating mean decrease in number of retching in control, test and standard group. The decrease in emesis due to extracts of various plants (*Adenanthera pavonina*, *Peltophorum roxburghii*, *Prosopis cineraria* and *P. juliflora*) was compared with controls and the standard and it was found that among all extracts, *P. juliflora* showed maximum antiemetic activity of 76.64% and minimum by chlorpromazine that reduced retches by 32.71% [67].

5.11. Antipustule activity

Pimple eradication is the hot core and important task for research in the cosmetic sector. They occur due to growth of Staphylococcus species whose biomass swells and develops as a pimple. Acetone extract of *P. juliflora* have anti-pustule activity which inhibit staphylococcus sp. that was explained by using well diffusion method. Rajadurai et al., found the minimum inhibitory concentration of acetone extract of *P. juliflora* and it was 0.75 mg/ml. FTIR was done to confirm the functional group and growth curve analysis was done for the determination of inhibitory action of acetone extract. The extract when used with synthetic creams increase the anti-pustule activity because with the extract the activity was increased and chances of skin blackening, itching of skin and damage of tissue due to synthetic creams are decreased [68].

5.12. Antigiardial and Amoebicidal activity

Giardiasis is caused due to parasitic gastro-intestinal diseases and affected 200 million people globally. *Giardia lamblia* is considered as one of the main causatives means of diarrhoea in both children and adults. Leaves of *P. juliflora* that are extracted (Petroleum ether and methanol) were taken and tests were performed at different concentrations. The highest effective concentration of *P. juliflora* petroleum ether extract against *Giardia lamblia* was 1000 ppm with mortality of 78.91% after 72 hours and the same extract show lowest anti giardial activity in 24 hours with 1000 ppm concentration have mortality rate of 38.55 %. While 312.5 ppm of metronidazole was given 83.42% mortality after 72 hours. After malaria and schistosomiasis, *Entamoeba histolytica* stood at third position in the world in causing lethal infection. Although it is asymptomatic in nearly 90% of cases, the symptoms of amoebiasis are hemorrhagic colitis and amoebic liver abscess which affect 50 million people all over the world. The highest effective concentration of *P. juliflora* methanol extract against *Entamoeba histolytica* was 1000 ppm with mortality of 71.97% after 72 hours. While 125 ppm concentration in petroleum ether extract is the lowest anti amoebic concentration with 31.88 % mortality in 24 hours. Also, 312.5 ppm of metronidazole gave 78.01% mortality after 72 hours. It has been concluded by Garbi et al., that the petroleum extract of *P. juliflora* leaves in both cases was better than the metronidazole which has been demonstrated to have side effects [69].

5.13. Cholinesterase inhibitory activity

Choudhary et al. investigated that *P. juliflora* contains alkaloids such as juliflorine which inhibit acetylcholinesterase and butyryl cholinesterase in non-competitive manner with IC₅₀ value 0.42 and 0.12 μ M and Ki values 0.4 and 0.1 μ M respectively. It was also confirmed by molecular docking in which the alkaloid interacts with the active site of acetylcholinesterase and it also blocks calcium channels. It was confirmed by human neutrophils viability assay which make juliflorine as an interesting alkaloid for Alzheimer diseases. Juliflorine also showed dose dependent (30-500 μ g/ml) spasmolytic and calcium channel blocking activity in isolated jejunum of rabbit [48].

5.14. Anti-inflammatory activity

The study was designed by Choudhary and Nagori, to phytochemically screen the anti-inflammatory potency of the ethanolic extract of *P. juliflora* leaves (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg) against carrageenan induced paw edema in rats. The phytochemical screening showed that flavonoids, saponins, carbohydrates, cardiac glycosides, tannins, and alkaloids are present in ethanolic extract of *P. juliflora* leaves. The oral median lethal dose (LD) of ethanolic extract was found to be 3807.9 mg/kg and > 5000 mg/kg in mice and rats respectively. The extract of *P. juliflora* shows highest activity at a dose of 400 mg/kg at which paw edema is attenuated. This study has been supported the traditional belief that *P. juliflora* used in the management of inflammations [70].

6. Toxicity studies

Toxicity refers to the harmful interaction between chemicals and biological systems. A toxicant is any substance that has harmful effects on a living system. *P. juliflora* or mesquite or algarroba parts are used by both animals as well as by human beings due to their beneficial effects. But sometimes due to consumption, intoxication is seen in animals, mainly in ruminant animals (in USA, Peru, Brazil). Mesquite is a very common plant in dry areas and easily available but the reports showed that it also causes animal poisoning due to the consumption of pods [71]. A disease known as “Caratorta” is most common in the ruminant animals specially in goats and cattle. In this the lateral deviation of the head occurs due to cranial nerve dysfunction, degeneration and disappearance of neurons in the trigeminal motor nucleus which perform to keep food in the mouth during mastication. This disease occurs only in those animals which eat *P. juliflora* pods for 8 months or more [29,71]. Also, other clinical signs during rumination are seen like dysphagia, incoordination of chewing movements, atrophy, dysphagia and profuse salivation of the masseter muscle in animals, ruminal atony, anemia, submandibular edema and progressive weight loss [72]. All the symptoms result in degradation of brain flora like neuromuscular alteration, histologic lesions like spongiosis, gliosis, the loss of Nissl granules, fine

vacuolation of the perikaryon of neurons from trigeminal motor nuclei and finally which results in the degeneration and disappearance of neuronal cells in the trigeminal motor nucleus [72,73].

A toxicity study was performed by Silva et al. on *P. juliflora* plant which leads to the isolation, purification, identification of juliprosopina and juliprosinene from the mixture of alkaloids. The study shows that piperidine alkaloids show toxicity in laboratory animals because they act directly on neural cells causing intracellular impairments, principally to mitochondria. Neural cell cultures technique was used to understand the main cellular alterations seen in “cara torta” disease and the mechanism of action of piperidine alkaloids which is the main neurotoxic compound in *P. juliflora* leaves and pods. This study showed that autophagy shows protective mechanisms for neural cells against programmed cell death started by mitochondrial damage [74].

P. juliflora also induces glial cell activation, cytotoxicity and NO production and this was explained by using rat astrocyte culture medium. The culture was treated with the total alkaloid extract of *P. juliflora* leaves and its chromatographic fractions to understand the direct effect of these metabolites and the toxicity. LDH activity and MTT test was done to reveal that TAE and other alkaloids fractions in culture medium were cytotoxic to astrocytes or vice versa [75].

To understand neurotoxicity and mechanism of action of juliprosopine alkaloid in isolated mitochondria of rat, potential toxicity study of *P. juliflora* was done by Mailoi et al. evaluation of different concentration (5–25 μM) of extract revealed that juliprosine mostly affect the membrane potential of neuronal cells, stimulate respiration (10–25 μM) and also effect ATP production in high concentration (15 and 25 μM). The result explained that cell death, dysfunction of cell and neurotoxicity occur due to uncoupling of oxidative phosphorylation, which reduced ATP production in neuronal cells [76].

Mani et al., studied acute toxicity, in which animals were observed for toxicity for 72 hours by administering the *P. juliflora* extract orally at doses ranging from 50-500 mg/kg and there were no toxic symptoms seen below dose level of 200 mg/kg. Also, subacute toxicity study shows that there is no change in the parameters like hematological, biochemical, renal and liver function parameters when dose of 200 mg/kg were given for 30 days or more. All the parameters were same in experimental animals on 31st day when animals are sacrificed and blood and serum samples were analyzed for various biochemical parameters. These results showed that ethanolic extract of *P. juliflora* is nontoxic and the concentration was further used for long term in-vivo studies for various pharmacological activity [77].

7. Patents of *Prosopis juliflora*

S.No.	Patent number	Title	Date	Ref.
1	WO2019193109A1	Cosmetic composition comprising a polysaccharide, surfactants and fragments of one or more plants	10/10/2019	[78]
2	BR102012030155A2	Additive Based on alkaloid extract of mesquite pods (<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>) in feeds, using as ruminal fermentation modifier for the improvement of animal performance and mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions.	23/07/2013	[79]
3	BR102017006458-1 A2	Cosmetic compositions containing <i>Prosopis juliflora</i> extracts	30/10/2018	[80]
4	WO2007029271A2	Glutathione-s-transferase gene from <i>Prosopis juliflora</i> confers abiotic stress tolerance in plants	15/03/2007	[81]
5	WO2011009184A1	Use of <i>Prosopis juliflora</i> for producing a water- based, xanthan gum-like polysaccharide polymer	27/01/2011	[82]

6	US5,824,312	Sunscreen agents from natural sources	20/10/1998	[83]
7	BR 102016020554A2	Froze milk derivative using vegetable hemicellulose	02/05/2018	[84]
8	US 8,298,991 B2	Method for controlling undesired Mimosaceae vegetation	30/10/2012	[85]
9	4,849,337	Assaying allergen specific IgE levels with fluorogenic enzyme labeled antibody.	18/07/1989	[86]
10	US2898260A	Fiber board and process of making same from desert shrubs	04/08/1959	[87]
11	BRPI1107317A2	Food composition, nutritional bar, and food composition production process comprehending melipone pollen	12/12/2017	[88]
12	US 8,372,989 B2	Polypeptides and biosynthetic pathways for the production of Stereroisomers of monatin and its precursors	07/05/2013	[89]
13	US 2008/0138496 A1	Preparation of Smoke Extract	12/06/2008	[90]
14	WO 2009/021661 A1	Composition for the prophylaxis and treatment of osteoporosis	19/02/2009	[91]
15	WO 2012/112518 A1	Interfering RNAs that promote root growth	23/08/2012	[92]
16	BRPI1106864A2	Topical and oral photo-protective formulations containing Brazilian vegetable extracts and/or oils	19/07/2016	[93]

8. Conclusion

From the above review, it is concluded that *P. juliflora* contain various medicinal properties. It is used traditionally by people to complete their needs as mentioned in various literatures. *P. juliflora* has been proved to be effective as anthelmintic, antioxidant, antipyretic, cytotoxicity effect, antiangiogenic, amoebicidal, anti pustule activity and many more. It is versatile and widely applicable in the food, cosmetic, pharmaceutical, agricultural and renewable energy industries. It also provides benefit for the progress in several fields of science and technology. "Cara torta" is the diseases caused by excess eating of pods of *P. juliflora* is characterized by neuro-muscular alterations like emaciation, muscular atrophy of the masseter muscles, spongiosis, neuronal degeneration, and gliosis. Also, it was clear from literature that autophagy plays an important protective mechanism for neural cells against programmed cell death started by mitochondrial damage. The presence of bioactive metabolites in this plant can be used in development of new pharmaceuticals that address largely unmet therapeutic needs in our society.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Burkart A. A monograph of the genus *Prosopis* (leguminosae subfam. mimosoideae). Journal of Arnold Arboretum. 1976; 57(4): 219–249.
- [2] Patil J, Kuppast IJ, Kumar KMA, Kishan KG. *Prosopis juliflora*, Research Journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacodynamics. 2016; 8(4): 5958.
- [3] Khandelwal P, Sharma RA, Agarwal M. Phytochemical analyses of various parts of *Prosopis juliflora*. Mintage Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Sciences. 2016; 5(1): 16–18.
- [4] Prasad MNV, Tewari JC. *Prosopis juliflora* (SW) DC: Potential for bioremediation and bioeconomy. Bioremediation and Bioeconomy, (Elsevier Inc.). 2016; 49-76.
- [5] Choge SK, Pasiecznik NM, Harvey M, Wright J, Awan SZ, et al. *Prosopis* pods as human food, with special reference to Kenya. Water SA. 2017; 33(3): 419–424.
- [6] Kailappan R, Gothandapani L, Viswanathan R. Production of activated carbon from *Prosopis juliflora*. Bioresource Technology. 2000; 75(3): 241–243.
- [7] Goel VL, Behl HM. Genetic selection and improvement of hard wood tree species for fuelwood production on sodic soil with particular reference to *Prosopis juliflora*. Biomass and Bioenergy. 2001; 20(1): 9–15.
- [8] Ukande MD, Shaikh S, Murthy K, Shete R. Review on Pharmacological potentials of *Prosopis juliflora*. Journal of Drug Delivery Therapeutics. 2019; 9(4-s): 755–760.
- [9] Dahms H, Sethuraman P. Pharmacological potentials of phenolic compounds from *Prosopis* spp. - A review. Journal of Coastal Life Medicine. 2015; 2(11): 918-924.
- [10] Wassel GM, Rizk AM, Abdel-Bary EF. Phytochemical investigation of *Prosopis juliflora* DCI Flavonoids and free sugars. Qualitas Plantarum et Materiae Vegetabiles. 1972; 22(1): 119–121.
- [11] Ibrahim M, Nadir M, Ali A, Ahmad VU, Rasheed M. Phytochemical analyses of *Prosopis juliflora* Swartz DC. Pakistan Journal of Botany. 2013; 45(6): 2101–2104.
- [12] Tewari JC, Harris PJC, Harsh LN, Ladoret K, Pasiecznik NM. Managing *Prosopis juliflora* (Vilazati Babul). Food and agriculture organisation. 2000; 1–20.
- [13] Shackleton RT, Le Maitre DC, Pasiecznik NM, Richardson DM. *Prosopis*: A global assessment of the biogeography, benefits, impacts and management of one of the world’s worst woody invasive plant taxa. AoB Plants. 2014; 6: 1–18.
- [14] Shiferaw H, Teketay D, Nemomissa S, Assefa F. Some biological characteristics that foster the invasion of *Prosopis juliflora* (Sw.) DC. at Middle Awash Rift Valley Area, north-eastern Ethiopia. Journal of Arid Environments. 2004; 58(2): 135–154.
- [15] Dave PN, Bhandari J. *Prosopis juliflora*: A review. International Journal of Chemical Studies. 2013; 1(3): 181–196.
- [16] Pasiecznik N, Felker P, Harris P, Harsh L, Cruz G, et al. The '*Prosopis juliflora*'-'*Prosopis pallida*' complex: a monograph. Forest Trees and Livelihoods. 2002; 12: 229–229.
- [17] Shitanda D, Mukonyi K, Kagiri M, Gichua M, Simiyu L. Properties of *Prosopis juliflora* and Its Potential Uses in Asal Areas of Kenya. Journal of Agriculture, Science and Technology. 2013; 15(1), 15–27.
- [18] Asadollahi K, Abassi N, Afshar N, Alipour M, Asadollahi P. Investigation of the effects of *Prosopis farcta* plant extract on Rat’s aorta. Journal of Medicinal Plants Research. 2010; 4(2): 142–147.
- [19] Asoiro FU, Nwoke OA, Ezenne GI. Some engineering properties of *Prosopis africana* (Okpeye) seeds. Journal of Agricultural Engineering and Technology. 2013; 21(2): 66-79.
- [20] Marwat SK, Rehman FU. Medicinal folk recipes used as traditional phytotherapies in district Dera Ismail Khan, KPK, Pakistan. Pakistan Journal of Botany. 2011; 43(3): 1453–1462.
- [21] Garg A, Mittal SK. Review on *Prosopis cineraria*: A potential herb of Thar desert. Drug Invention Today. 2013; 5(1): 60–65.

- [22] Preeti K, Avatar SR, Mala A. Pharmacology and Therapeutic Application of *Prosopis juliflora*: A Review, Journal of Plant Sciences. 2015; 3(4): 234.
- [23] Singh S. Phytochemical analysis of different parts of *Prosopis juliflora*. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. 2012; 4(3): 59–61.
- [24] Raghavendra MP, Satish S, Raveesha KA. Alkaloids isolated from leaves of *Prosopis juliflora* against *Xanthomonas* pathogens. Archives of Phytopathology and Plant Protection. 2009; 42(11): 1033–1041.
- [25] Ahmad VU, Qazi S. The absolute configuration of julifloridine. Zeitschrift Für Naturforschung B. 1983; 38(5): 660.
- [26] Ahmad VU, Basha A and Haque W. New alkaloids from *Prosopis juliflora* DC. Zeitschrift für Naturforschung B. 1978; 33(3): 347–348.
- [27] Ahmad VU, Sultana A, Qazi S. Alkaloids from the leaves of *Prosopis juliflora*. Journal of Natural Products. 1989; 52(3): 497–501.
- [28] Uddin Ahmad V, Sultana A. A terpenoid diketone from the leaves of *Prosopis juliflora*, Phytochemistry. 1989; 28(1): 278–279.
- [29] Tabosa IM, Cluintans-Júnior LJ, Pamplona FV, Almeida RN, Cunha EVL da, et al. Isolamento biomonitorado de alcalóides tóxicos de *Prosopis juliflora* (algaroba). Revista Brasileira de Farmacognosia. 2000; (1): 9-10.
- [30] Tapia A, Egly Feresin G, Bustos D, Astudillo L, Theoduloz C, et al. Biologically active alkaloids and a free radical scavenger from *Prosopis* species. Journal of Ethnopharmacology. 2000; 71(1–2): 241–246.
- [31] Rahman AA, Samoylenko V, Jacob MR, Sahu R, Jain SK, et al. Antiparasitic and antimicrobial indolizidines from the leaves of *Prosopis glandulosa* var. *glandulosa*. Planta Medica. 2011; 77(14): 1639–1643.
- [32] dos Santos ET, Pereira MLA, da Silva CFPG, Souza-Neta LC, Geris R, et al. Antibacterial activity of the alkaloid-enriched extract from *Prosopis juliflora* pods and its influence on in Vitro ruminal digestion. International Journal Molecular Sciences. 2013; 14(4): 8496–8516.
- [33] Shachi Singh, Swapnil SKV. Antibacterial properties of Alkaloid rich fractions obtained from various parts of *Prosopis juliflora*. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research. 2011; 2(3): 114–120.
- [34] Nakano H, Nakajima E, Hiradate S, Fujii Y, Yamada K, et al. Growth inhibitory alkaloids from mesquite (*Prosopis juliflora* (Sw.) DC.) leaves. Phytochemistry. 2004; 65(5): 587–591.
- [35] Sirmah P, Mburu F, Iaych K, Dumarçay S, Gérardin P. Potential antioxidant compounds from different parts of *Prosopis juliflora*. Journal of Tropical Forest Sciences. 2011; 23(2): 187–195.
- [36] Nakano H, Fujii Y, Suzuki T, Yamada K, Kosemura S, et al. A growth-inhibitory substance exuded from freeze-dried mesquite (*Prosopis juliflora* (Sw.) DC.) leaves. Plant Growth Regulation. 2011; 33(3): 165–168.
- [37] Nakano H, Fujii Y, Yamada K, Kosemura S, Yamamura S, et al. Isolation and identification of plant growth inhibitors as candidate(s) for allelopathic substance(s) from aqueous leachate from mesquite (*Prosopis juliflora* (Sw.) DC.) leaves. Plant Growth Regulation. 2002; 37(2): 113–117.
- [38] Azevedo G, Damasceno DB, & Giordani RB, *Prosopis juliflora* (SW) DC. An invasive species at the Brazilian Caatinga : phytochemical, pharmacological, toxicological and technological overview. Phytochemistry Reviews. 2017; 17: 309–331.
- [39] Astudillo L, Schmeda-Hirschmann G, Herrera JP, Cortés M. Proximate composition and biological activity of Chilean *Prosopis* species. Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture. 2000; 80(5): 567–573.
- [40] Dewick PM. Medicinal natural products: a biosynthetic approach, (John Wiley & Sons). 2002.
- [41] Wink M, Schimmer O. Molecular modes of action of defensive secondary metabolites. Annual Plant Reviews online. 2018; 21–161.
- [42] Patel VJ, Safaya V. The Role of *Prosopis* in Wasteland Development. Jivrajbhai Patel Agrofor Center, Surendrabag, Gujarat, India. 1986.
- [43] Cruz G, Del Re B, Amado R. Contribución al estudio de la composición química de los frutos maduros del algarrobo. III Jornadas Peruanas Fitoquímica. 1987; 122.
- [44] Sáenz G, Serra JA, Escriche I. Composición química de la algarroba peruana (*Prosopis* sp.). In: Proc. 2nd Int. Carob Symp. Generalitat Valenciana, Valencia, Spain. 1987; 419–427.

- [45] Singh G, Abrol IP, Cheema SS. Effects of irrigation on *Prosopis juliflora* and soil properties of an alkali soil. *International Tree Crops Journal*. 1990; 6(2–3): 81–99.
- [46] Sharma BM. Chemical analysis of some desert trees. In: *Proceedings. International Society for Tropical Ecology*. 1968; (1): 248.
- [47] Ahmad A, Khan KA, Ahmad V. Immunomodulating effect of preliminary report. *Immunology*. 1992; (8): 189–193.
- [48] Choudhary MI, Nawaz SA, Azim MK, Ghayur MN, Lodhi MA, et al. Juliflorine: A potent natural peripheral anionic-site-binding inhibitor of acetylcholinesterase with calcium-channel blocking potential, a leading candidate for Alzheimer's disease therapy, *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communication*. 2005; 332: 1171–1179.
- [49] Almaraz-Abarca N, da Graça Campos M, Ávila-Reyes JA, Naranjo-Jiménez N, Herrera Corral J, et al. Antioxidant activity of polyphenolic extract of monofloral honeybee-collected pollen from mesquite (*Prosopis juliflora*, Leguminosae). *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*. 2007; 20(2): 119–124.
- [50] Ravikumar S, Inbaneson SJ, Suganthi P. *In vitro* antiplasmodial activity of ethanolic extracts of South Indian medicinal plants against *Plasmodium falciparum*. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Diseases*. 2012; 2(3): 180–183.
- [51] Madhusudana R, Jagadeeshwar R, Ashok K, Jhillu S, Kondapuram VR. Antioxidant from natural source, US Pat 2004; 0116716.
- [52] Sathiyam M, Muthuchelian K. Investigation of Phytochemical Profile and Antibacterial Potential of Ethanolic Leaf Extract of *Prosopis juliflora* DC. *Ethnobotanical Leaflets*. 2008; 12: 1240–1245.
- [53] Simonsen HT, Nordskjold JB, Smitt UW, Nyman U, Palpu P, et al. *In vitro* screening of Indian medicinal plants for antiplasmodial activity. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2001; 74(2): 195–204.
- [54] Batista R, Santana CC, Azevedo-Santos AV, Suarez-Fontes AM, Ferraz JL de AA, et al. *In vivo* antimalarial extracts and constituents of *Prosopis juliflora* (Fabaceae). *Journal of Functional Foods*. 2018; 44: 74–78.
- [55] Mani S, Krishnaswamy M. Anti-tumor potential of total alkaloid extract of *Prosopis juliflora* DC. leaves against Molt-4 cells *in vitro*. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 2011; 10(44): 8881–8888.
- [56] Yadav R, Tikar SN, Sharma AK, Tyagi V, Sukumaran D, et al. Screening of some weeds for larvicidal activity against *Aedes albopictus*, A vector of dengue and chikungunya. *Journal of Vector Borne Diseases*. 2015; 52(1): 88–94.
- [57] Yadav R, Tyagi V, Tikar SN, Sharma AK, Mendki MJ, et al. Differential larval toxicity and oviposition altering activity of some indigenous plant extracts against dengue and Chikungunya vector *Aedes albopictus*. *Journal of Arthropod-Borne Diseases*. 2014; 8(2): 174–185.
- [58] Rechab SO, Kareru PG, Kutima HL, Nyaga GC, Njonge FK, et al. Phytochemical and *In vitro* anthelmintic studies of *Prosopis juliflora* (sw.) dc (fabaceae) extracts against *Haemonchus contortus*, an ovine nematode. *JKUAT annual scientific conference proceedings*. 2011; 173–178.
- [59] Raghavendra MP, Satish S, Raveesha KA. Alkaloid extracts of *Prosopis juliflora* (Sw.) DC. (Mimosaceae) against *Alternaria alternata*. *Journal of Biopesticides*. 2009; 2(1): 56–59.
- [60] Young DW. Factors Affecting the Translocation of Herbicides in Mesquite (*Prosopis juliflora*). 1950.
- [61] Cáceres A, Menéndez H, Méndez E, Cohobón E, Samayoa BE, et al. Antigonorrhoeal activity of plants used in Guatemala for the treatment of sexually transmitted diseases. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 1995; 48(2): 85–88.
- [62] Satish S, Raveesha KA, Janardhana GR. Antibacterial activity of plant extracts on phytopathogenic *Xanthomonas campestris* pathovars. *Letter in Applied Microbiology*. 1999; 28(2): 145–147.
- [63] Jian Z, Xun S. Antioxidant activities of baicalin, green tea polyphenols and alizarin *in vitro* and *in vivo*. *Journal of Nutrition and Environmental Medicine*. 1997; 7(2): 79–89.
- [64] Rice-Evans C. Screening of Phenolics and Flavonoids for Antioxidant Activity. *Antioxidant Food Supplements in Human Health*. 1999; 239–253.
- [65] Prasad OH, Navya a, Vasu D, Chiranjeevi T, Bhaskar M, et al. Protective effects of *Prosopis juliflora* against *Staphylococcus aureus* induced hepatotoxicity in rats. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Research*. 2011; 2(3): 172–178.

- [66] Gopinath SM, Reddy JM, Dayanand KS, Shankar A. To evaluate the antipyretic activity of *Prosopis juliflora* ethanolic extract in brewer's yeast induced hyperthermia in rats. *Journal of Biotechnology and Biosafety*. 2013; 28-32.
- [67] Ul Hasan MM, Azhar I, Muzammil S, Ahmed S, Ahmed SW. Anti-Emetic activity of some leguminous plants. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*. 2012; 44(1): 389–391.
- [68] Rajadurai Jesudoss RP, Lakshmi Praba S, Gnanasaraswathi M, Ganesh kumar S, Praveen kumar TG. Screening of anti-pustule plant metabolites from *Prosopis juliflora* and their combined anti- pustule activity with synthetic pimple creams. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2014; (2): 145–150.
- [69] Kabbashi AS, Garbi MI, Osman EE, Dahab MM, Koko WS, et al. Antigiardial, Amoebicidal and Cytotoxic activity of the plant *Prosopis juliflora* leave extracts. *Meriti Research Journal of Biochemistry and Bioinformatics*. 2015; 2(2): 2-8.
- [70] Choudhary PK, Nagori BP. Oral *Prosopis juliflora* treatment ameliorates inflammatory responses against carrageenan induced paw edema in rats. *Journal of Scientific and Innovative Research*. 2013; 2(5): 888–892.
- [71] Câmara ACL, Costa N de A, Riet-Correa F, Afonso JAB, Dantas AFM, et al. Intoxicação espontânea por vagens de *Prosopis juliflora* (Leg. Mimosoideae) em bovinos no Estado de Pernambuco. *Pesquisa Veterinária Brasileira*. 2009; 29(3): 233–240.
- [72] Tabosa IM, Riet-Correa F, Barros SS, Summers BA, Simões SVD, et al. Neurohistologic and ultrastructural lesions in cattle experimentally intoxicated with the plant *Prosopis juliflora*. *Veterinary Pathology*. 2006; 43(5): 695–701.
- [73] da Silva VDA, da Silva AMM, e Silva JHC, Costa SL. (2018). Neurotoxicity of *Prosopis juliflora*: from Natural Poisoning to Mechanism of Action of Its Piperidine Alkaloids. *Neurotoxicity Research*. 2018; 34(4): 878–888.
- [74] Silva VDA, Pitanga BPS, Nascimento RP, Souza CS, Coelho PLC, et al. Juliprosopine and Juliprosine from *Prosopis juliflora* Leaves Induce Mitochondrial Damage and Cytoplasmic Vacuolation on Cocultured Glial Cells and Neurons. *Chemical Research in Toxicology*. 2013; 24: 1810-1820.
- [75] Silva AMM, Silva AR, Pinheiro AM, Freitas SRVB, Silva VDA, et al. Alkaloids from *Prosopis juliflora* leaves induce glial activation, cytotoxicity and stimulate NO production. *Toxicol*. 2007; 49(5): 601–614.
- [76] Maioli MA, Lemos DECV, Guelfi M, Medeiros HCD, Riet-Correa F, et al. Mechanism for the uncoupling of oxidative phosphorylation by juliprosopine on rat brain mitochondria. *Toxicol*. 2012; 60(8): 1355–1362.
- [77] Mani P. Phytochemical and Pharmacological Analysis of Ethanolic Extracts of *Prosopis juliflora* (Sw.). *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2017; 6(9): 2059–2069.
- [78] Royale R. Cosmetic composition comprising a polysaccharide, surfactants and fragments of one or more. WIPO/PCT No. WO2019193109A1. 2019.
- [79] Pereira MLA, Batista R. Additive Based on alkaloid extract of mesquite pods (*Prosopis juliflora*) in feeds, using as ruminal fermentation modifier for the improvement of animal performance and mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions. Brazil patent No. BR102012030155A2. 2013.
- [80] Norte DO. Cosmetic composition containing *Prosopis juliflora* extracts, Brazil Patent No. BR102017006458-1. 2018.
- [81] Parida A, George S. Glutathione-S-transferase gene from *Prosopis juliflora* confers abiotic stress tolerance in plants. WIPO/PCT No. WO2007029271A2. 2010.
- [82] Buzanelli EQ, Fabi MT, Silva JFB Da, Rocha LJS, Buzanelli LP, et al. Use of *Prosopis juliflora* for producing a water-based, xanthan gum-like polysaccharide polymer. WIPO/PCT No. WO2011009184A1. 2011.
- [83] Unger EC, McCreery TP. Sunscreen agents from natural sources. U.S. Patent No. US5, 824,312. 1998.
- [84] Maria I, Gomes S, Frederico JB. Frozen milk derivative using vegetable hemicelluloses. Brazil Patent No. BR102016020554A2. 2018.
- [85] Turner R, Castner E. Method for controlling undesired mimosoideae vegetation. U.S. Patent No. US. 2012; 8, 298, 991 B2.
- [86] Calenoff E, Jones RM, Tsay Y-G, Scott JR. Assaying allergen specific IgE levels with fluorogenic enzyme labeled antibody. US Pat. 1989; 4, 849, 337.
- [87] Berliner JFT. Fiber board and process of making same from desert shrubs. U.S. Patent No. US2898260A. 1959.

- [88] Antonio BS, Maria F, Ana L. Food composition, nutritional bar, and food composition production process comprehending melipone pollen. Brazil Patent No. BRPI1107317A2. 2017.
- [89] Brazeau BJ, Souza ML De, Gort SJ, Hicks PM, Kollmann SR, et al. Polypeptides and biosynthetic pathways for the production of stereoisomers of monatin and their precursors. U.S. Patent No. US. 2008; 8, 372, 989 B2.
- [90] Plaschke K. Preparation of smoke extract. US Pat US 2008/0138496 A1. 2008.
- [91] Lang F, Nasir O. Composition for the prophylaxis and treatment of osteoporosis. WIPO/PCT No. WO 2009/021661 Al. 2009.
- [92] Huang X, Mcneill T, Schweiner M, Wittich P. Interfering rnas that promote root growth. WIPO/PCT No. WO 2012/112518 Al. 2012.
- [93] Caneschi C, Polonini H, Brandão M, Raposo N. Topical and oral photoprotective formulations containing Brazilian vegetable extracts and / or oils. Brazil Patent No. BRPI1106864A2. 2016.